

Exploitation of the SoilPRO® (SP) apparatus to measure soil surface reflectance in the field: Five case studies

Eyal Ben Dor^{a,*}, Amihai Granot^a, Rony Wallach^b, Nicolas Francos^a, Daniela Heller Pearlstein^a, Bar Efrati^a, Luboš Borůvka^c, Asa Gholizadeh^c, Thomas Schmid^d

^a Remote Sensing Laboratory, Geography Department, Porter School of the Environment and Earth Sciences, Faculty of Exact Sciences, Tel Aviv University, Tel Aviv 699780, Israel

^b Soil and Water Department, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Israel

^c Department of Soil Science and Soil Protection, Faculty of Agrobiological, Food and Natural Resources, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, Kamycka 129, Suchbát, Prague 16500, Czech Republic

^d Department of Environment, Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas (CIEMAT), Avda. Complutense, 40, 28040 Madrid, Spain

ARTICLE INFO

Handling Editor: Jingyi Huang

Keywords:

Soil reflectance
SoilPRO
Field measurements
Soil surface properties

ABSTRACT

The SoilPRO® (SP) is an assembly designed to acquire soil reflectance information in the field without disturbing the soil surface, and regardless of atmospheric and solar radiation conditions. This paper summarizes five case studies in which the SP assembly was used for different applications. The case studies consisted of: (1) generating surface spectral measurements under any atmospheric condition; (2) comparing the performance of the SP to the traditional bare fiber method for vicarious calibration of hyperspectral satellite sensors; (3) assessing water repellency of a soil surface governed by organic matter hydrophobicity; (4) spatial prediction of the rate of water infiltration into the soil profile as governed by the soil surface seal; and (5) using the SP apparatus to measure soil surface reflectance in South Shetland Island, Antarctica under severe weather conditions. The case studies included calculation of spectral quality, prediction accuracy and measurement stability. The paper discusses each of the cases in detail and concludes that the SP (or similar assembly) is the best way to measure the reflectance of the original soil surface in the field. In the first case study, the spectrum collected by the SP under daily changing illumination was shown to be stable relative to the traditional measurement methods of contact probe or bare fiber. The second case study indicated that use of the SP for vicarious calibration is much more efficient (in terms of time and stability) than ground-truth practice over a large area, and in the third case study, the SP was able to assess a soil surface property governed by organic matter hydrophobicity better than the contact probe, which destroys the soil surface organic seal. A similar achievement was gained in the fourth case study, providing a better assessment of the water-infiltration rate into the soil. In the fifth case study, the SP demonstrated impressive high-quality acquisition of soil surface reflectance with a very low sun angle over the South Pole. Based on these case studies and the high quality of the data generated by the SP in the field, we suggest building, in parallel to the classical soil spectral libraries generated in the laboratory, field soil spectral libraries that will preserve the soil surface properties scanned in the field. We anticipate the development of more applications for the SP assembly based on the capabilities shown in this paper.

1. Introduction

Soil reflectance measurement across the visible–near infrared–shortwave infrared (VIS–NIR–SWIR; 350–2500 nm) region is one of the most practical means for both proximal and remote sensing of soil attributes (Viscarra Rossel et al., 2016; Behera et al., 2022). It has become a common technique for predicting several soil properties in the

laboratory—more rapidly than the traditional wet chemistry methods with reliable accuracy (Ben-Dor and Banin, 1995; Viscarra Rossel et al., 2006; Stenberg et al., 2010). Accordingly, it is widely used not only in the laboratory but also in the field. In general, soil spectral information is gathered into a soil spectral library (SSL) database consisting of both spectral and chemical information. Such libraries are mainly constructed in the laboratory with spectral measurements performed under

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: benedor@tauex.tau.ac.il (E.B. Dor).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2023.116636>

Received 18 March 2023; Received in revised form 3 August 2023; Accepted 4 August 2023

Available online 11 August 2023

0016-7061/© 2023 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

controlled conditions (e.g. geometry, grain size, illumination, and moisture content). Soil reflectance measurements in the field are strongly affected by atmospheric attenuation, changes in the sun's elevation, user stability and experience, spectral protocol configuration, surface variations, unstable geometry, and the measurement means (Milton et al., 2009). These lead to uncertainties in the data, and lower accuracy under outdoor conditions (Christy, 2008; Gomez et al., 2008; Wenjun et al., 2014; Rodionov et al., 2015). Minimizing these effects is therefore essential and requires frequent calibration, resulting in a high volume of measurements for a given target, together with extensive documentation of the environmental conditions during the spectral acquisition, resulting in a small number of samples per unit time. These effects therefore hinder accurate comparisons between spectra and, further, do not allow quantitative analysis of the acquired spectral information.

Today, high volumes of field measurements are performed mostly with a bare fiber (BF) fore optic, which suffers from all of the above-listed issues. Another method is to measure soil reflectance in the field using a contact probe (CP) device (Wenjun et al., 2014) a common assembly used in the laboratory that touches the soil surface with an area of about 12 cm². However, this option suffers from poor representative area, poor contact with irregular surfaces, sensitivity to holding stability, and in some cases, it can harm the fragile soil surface seal due to probe pressure on the soil surface. There are other ways to extract soil spectral information in the field without harming the soil surface, such as deploying a goniometer or constructing a stable and fixed fore-optic geometry with artificial illumination (e.g. Wise and Mars, 2022).

The last few years have seen the development of assemblies that can overcome some of the limitations inherent in spectral acquisition under field conditions (Milton, 2010; Milton et al., 2009). Some of these self-developed tools make use of an internal illumination source, either inside the probe, as a modification of available devices (Kusumo, 2018), or in an isolated chamber, for surface and subsurface use (Rodionov et al., 2015), to ensure stable radiation intensity without any atmospheric attenuation. However, these tools are heavy and cannot be carried by an ordinary operator; they require a tractor tow, which may demolish the fragile surface seal, and are not suitable for field and ground-truth work.

In general, a standard method for measuring soil surface reflectance in the field should be robust, rapid, representative, and as reproducible and as close to the measurements performed in the laboratory as possible (i.e., enabling extraction of the same spectrum over the same area with no change in its nature, thus allowing the exploitation of the many SSLs in the laboratory). Accordingly, alternative methods and protocols for measuring soil spectral information in the field are strongly required. The technique must represent the soil surface precisely as it is seen from a remote domain (i.e., a natural surface), cover a sizeable representative area, and overcome all the other aforementioned problems (i.e., user effect, geometry stability, surface characteristics, atmospheric attenuation (plus clouds) and changes in sun angle). In this context, Ben-Dor et al. (2017) developed a simple soil field probe assembly named "SoilPRO®" (SP) (U.S. Patent Office Serial No. 15407295). This device can be hooked up to any portable spectrometer furnished with a fiber-optic cable and has already demonstrated remarkable results in fieldwork scenarios. Ben-Dor et al. (2017) showed that the SP performs spectral measurements with laboratory quality, which are stable, even when taken by different non-skilled users. We thus exploited this assembly in different applications, where the soil surface controls field properties, and under different atmospheric conditions in the field. This paper reports on five case studies in which the soil's thin surface must be preserved to accurately approximate the soil surface properties by spectroscopy. The SP was used by several independent users, and the results are reported herein. Our intention is mainly to open the way to other applications requiring high-quality soil reflectance products under extreme measurement conditions.

2. General materials and methods

2.1. Soil field probe

The SP apparatus was used in all of the presented case studies. It was designed at Tel Aviv University and is patented under U.S. Patent Office Serial No. 15407295. It is composed of an aluminum cylinder (painted matte "Kodak" black inside) with a diameter of 24 cm and height of 25 cm, weighing 1.6 kg. The device is furnished with a fiber-optic holder that maintains a stable geometry for both illumination and viewing angle (Ben-Dor et al., 2017). The viewing angle is 45°, enabling measurement of an area of about 1800 cm² with a BF of 25° field of view (FOV). The assembly's target dimensions were designed to align with the commonly used 25 cm × 25 cm (10 × 10 square inch) Spectralon (Labsphere®) white reference panel, for optimal performance of white reference measurements as relative reflectance for each measurement. On top of the cylinder, a stabilized tungsten halogen lamp uniformly illuminates the surface at a nadir angle. To use the SP illuminator lamp (Analytical Spectral Devices (ASD) ProLamp® and Ushio® bulb model JC14.5V-50 WC) in the field, we attached a power supply adapter (12 V DC to 15 V DC and 220 V AC to 15 V DC according to the bulb specifications). The adapter provides a stable input voltage to the bulb from any grid or portable power source during operation and indicates any power instability or faulty battery. For the SP prototype, we used a lightweight portable lithium-ion battery (11.1 V, 31.2 Ah, 1.98 kg), which could operate for about 5 h and, in contrast to other commonly used CP tools, it does not consume precious power from the field spectrometer's battery. The fiber optic from the ASD FieldSpec® (model FSP 350-2500P) is connected via an adapter to a mount attached to the conical aluminum side addition of the chamber to position its fore optic at a 45° angle for maximum target area. This configuration is designed to maintain minimal specular reflection and maximal Lambertian radiation collection from the target below, as well as to simulate the geometry of the ASD CP (ASD Inc., n.d.) apparatus and the illumination unit's operating protocol as suggested by ASD Inc. (2012). Fig. 1 provides the SP scheme and all of the system's accessories, and Fig. 2 illustrates the operating principle as demonstrated by a single operator.

The operating scheme of the SP is similar to that for laboratory spectral data measurements. The spectrometer has to be warmed up for 60 min, the bulb for 15 min and the rim of the SP periphery has to be cleaned with a soft white paper. For configuration and white reference calibration, the assembly has to be deployed on a 10 square inch white reference (Spectralon) (see Fig. 2c). The spectral configuration consists of 30 readings for samples, white reference and black current. Optimization has to be established, just as in the laboratory, as the measurement scheme reflectance is relative to the white reference, and a stable and straight reflectance line of 100% has to be achieved for the white reference sample. The SP behaves as a real dark chamber as no SP signal occurs during a sunny day and high sun elevation condition while the bulb was shut off. Soil measurement is done by gently placing the SP surface rim on the soil surface to avoid any leakage of light from the inner SP volume.

2.2. Statistical evaluation

To evaluate the spectral similarity in our case studies, we conducted statistical analyses of root mean square error (RMSE, Eq. (1)), ratio of performance to interquartile distance (RPIQ, Eq. (2)), and the average sum of deviations squared (ASDS, Eq. (3)).

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2}{n}} \quad (1)$$

$$RPIQ = IQ/RMSE \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Left: Sketch of the SoilPRO device (profile view). Right: SoilPRO system setup configuration (top view). (1) main body, (2) illumination source, (3) illumination beam, (4) optic fiber, (5) fiber holder, (6) fiber FOV, (7) handle, (8) power adapter, (9) power cord, (10) portable battery, (11) ASD Field Spec Pro spectrometer and operating laptop.

Fig. 2. Use of SoilPRO in the field. (a, b) Ease of carrying the portable spectrometer over different areas, (c) white reference calibration process, (d) surface measurement.

$$ASDS = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n ((Y_i/\hat{Y}_i) - 1)^2}{n} \quad (3)$$

where \hat{Y} is the predicted value, Y is the observed value of the number of data points, and IQ is the interquartile distance of the measured value. These statistics were used according to each of the case studies' requirements.

3. Case studies

Sections 3.1–3.5 present five case studies in which the SoilPro® (SP) was utilized. It is noteworthy that, in all instances, precise measurement of the uppermost layer of delicate soil, under undisturbed outdoor conditions such as surface and radiation, was crucial. Each case is accompanied by a thorough description of the problem addressed by the SP, a comprehensive description of the methodology employed to attain the solution, and a detailed analysis of the resulting outcomes and derived conclusions.

3.1. Case study 1: All conditions – 24/7 field spectral measurements

To evaluate the reliability of the SP's performance in measuring surface reflectance in the field while avoiding the aforementioned problems such as poor outdoor radiation, five soil samples from Israel

Table 1
Soil samples selected for the SP exercise.

Sample	Israeli name	Definition	USDA Great Group soil taxonomy
A	Hamra	Brownish red sandy soil	Haploxeralfs
B	Rendzina	Rendzina mountain soil	Rendolls
C	Vertisol	Brown alluvial soil	Chromoxererts
D	Loess	Loess raw soil	Camborthids
E	Coastal beach sand	Coastal beach sand	Torripsamments

representing five different USDA orders (see Table 1 and Fig. 3) were selected. All samples were collected from the upper 5 cm, brought to the laboratory, air-dried, and sieved to pass a 2 mm sieve. Each soil was placed on a shallow aluminum plate painted matte black with a diameter of 30 cm and thickness of 2 cm to completely fill the SP's area diameter of 25 cm. The aim was to examine the stability of the SP apparatus relative to BF practices over several soil types and with changing sun elevation and atmospheric conditions.

The reflectance of each soil was incrementally acquired on 23 May 2020 using a BF, outside the laboratory under a clear sky, and then using the SP for 8 h (08:30–16:30 h). At 12:30 h, clouds appeared temporarily during the measurements. Therefore, two measurements were acquired at that time, with and without clouds. The BF was mounted on a tripod facing nadir and covering the soil target with a 30% margin (area of 1000 cm²). Fig. 4 shows the spectra throughout the day as measured with the SP and BF.

Regarding the SP measurements, it can be noticed that a stable and constant reflectance was delivered throughout the day (Fig. 4), with no variance in albedo value or spectral shape for the spectra taken at different times. Only a minor variation in albedo was seen in sample (d) at 12:30 h, but the spectrum still satisfied our expectation of stability. In contrast, the BF measurements showed variations in albedo at each time point due to the instability of the atmospheric conditions and changes in sun angle. Marginal changes appeared during the clouds' appearance at 12:30 h with the BF (Fig. 4). We assume that those changes were the result of bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) effects due to the changing solar elevation and stable nadir viewing angle, as well as the inconsistent illumination due to the passing clouds. In Fig. 4 (bare fiber), two extreme white reference values are shown: in the one that is lower than 100% reflectance, the white reference was measured when the clouds were passing over, and is relative to the white reference standard which was measured under a clear sky; the one that is higher than 100% was measured under a clear sky, and is relative to the white reference measured under a cloudy sky. The stable results of the SP measurements suggest that it can provide accurate and stable readings despite the uncertainties arising from atmosphere, illumination, measurement geometry, and user experience.

This examination confirmed the ability of the SP assembly to acquire stable field measurements, while leaving the soil surface undisturbed (i. e., preserving it in its natural state under constant illumination and geometry). It can serve as a rapid measurement tool to develop a field SSL in parallel to a laboratory SSL, which will enable obtaining field information and reliable ground-truth measurements (Milton et al., 2009). Francos and Ben-Dor (2022) recently established a transfer function to estimate field reflectance from a laboratory SSL using mutual measurements with the field (SP) and laboratory (CP) SSL protocols. In addition, this device can close the gap, when soil spectral information is needed under extreme conditions such as during the night, avoiding complicated measurement schemes as conducted, for example, by Wise and Mars (2022).

3.2. Case study 2: Vicarious calibration of hyperspectral sensors from the ground

Hyperspectral (HSR) sensors require periodic radiometric and spectral calibration. Aside from onboard calibration routines (e.g., partial-aperture calibrators, standard lamps, and solar diffuser panels) (Thenkabail, 2016), vicarious calibration (VC) practices are the most useful method for examining and rectifying the sensor's radiometric and spectral response, and checking its thematic performance (Xu et al., 2020). The VC method uses natural or artificial sites on the ground for the post-launch calibration of sensors and spectral measurements of these sites that precisely represent the reflectance of the area with high fidelity (Morain and Budge, 2004). Accordingly, VC is a significant part of many groups' activity worldwide, and those who operate and use HSR data invest a great deal of effort in the calibration/validation (CAL/VAL) of the mission at hand, such as the IEEE P4001 (<https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/4001/7314/>) working group, the GEO working group, the CAL/VAL Working Groups of Surface Biology and Geology (SBG) (Kokaly and Turpie, 2019), and the RadCalNetWorking group (Bouvet et al., 2019).

The most common way to carry out VC is to use natural and homogeneous ground targets on earth that are stable in space and time. The measurement is conducted during or close to the sensor's overpass time, estimating top of the atmosphere (TOA) radiance at-sensor. The critical issue in VC is the measurement of the ground reflectance in a very precise, reliable, and representative way, very close to or during the overpass. This is also true for any other ground-truth mission and hence requires a carefully executed protocol and method.

In general, to achieve representative reflectance on the ground for the mission, ground spectral measurements are well-planned, with several known protocols. In addition, the VC area should be stable with minimum changes over time, and it should allow for frequent and repeated ground measurements. Due to today's availability of portable spectrometers, there are many protocols for acquiring field reflectance measurements, from just pointing the BF at a nadir-looking angle manually to using a goniometer; both rely on solar radiation and are strongly affected by the atmosphere's attenuation and the sun's elevation (e.g. Stoner et al. 1980, Peddle et al. 2001, Schopfer, 2008, Kodaira and Shibusawa, 2013, Labarre et al 2019). Another common practice is to use a CP furnished with artificial illumination while touching the surface for measurements. In each of these methods, samples representing the selected and stable area are needed where several limitations, such as sensitivity to the measurement geometry and even to the color of the clothes that the users are wearing, matter (SVC, 2019). The goniometer apparatus is a good method for a single measurement but cannot cover large areas, whereas the CP assembly, which can do so, is problematic as it has a very small area. In addition, it may destroy the surface due to the need to contact the fragile ground. To avoid some of these problems, Ray Kokaly (personal communication, 2022) developed a portable assembly that simultaneously measures the upwelling and downwelling radiation at a constant geometry, thereby minimizing some of the main uncertainties (recently, a new concept termed ASD Field Spec Dual has also been adopted to overcome these obstacles; htt

Fig. 3. Five soil samples used for case study 1 (see Table 1). According to the USDA Great Group Soil Taxonomy, these soils are: (a) Haploxeralfs, (b) Rendolls, (c) Chromoxererts, (d) Camborthids, (e) Torripsamments.

Fig. 4. Case study 1 spectra from bare fiber (top) vs. SoilPRO (bottom) of soils a–e (see Table 1) at different times and under a clear and cloudy sky at 12:30 h. White Reference (WR).

[ps://www.malvernpanalytical.com/en/products/product-range/asd-range/fieldspec-range/software/fieldspec-dual](https://www.malvernpanalytical.com/en/products/product-range/asd-range/fieldspec-range/software/fieldspec-dual).

In this case study, our aim was to minimize, using the SP apparatus, the effects of measurement geometry, atmospheric attenuation, and sun elevation changes during the short time of the sensor's overpass. Accordingly, we examined the SP's performance during a real calibration mission over a well-known VC site selected for HSR performance—Amiaz plain in southern Israel ($31^{\circ}04' 20.98''\text{N}$, $35^{\circ}22'14.83''\text{E}$). The area is in the Judean Desert (Fig. 5) and is a homogeneous bright-surface playa ($5 \text{ km} \times 5 \text{ km}$) with high reflectance values (>0.4). Because vegetation is scarce and it is stable in space and time, it was selected for the radiometric evaluation and cross-calibration of PRISMA, DESIS, EnMAP and EMIT orbital sensors (Heller-Pearlshtien et al., 2021, 2023; Heller-Pearlshtien and Ben-Dor, 2022).

During August 2021 and August 2022, and close to the overpass of EnMAP and EMIT sensors, we conducted VC measurements over the area. We used the EnMAP measurement protocol (Heller-Pearlshtien et al., 2023) that captures measurements of a $90 \text{ m} \times 90 \text{ m}$ area and the

SP measurement protocol for the VC mission. Fig. 5 provides the scheme of the EnMAP measurements from August 2022. An ASD BF with 25° fore optics was also used from a height of 1.5 m covering an area of about 1800 cm^2 . The measurements were conducted on a clear morning, and the users maintained a stable geometry of back to the sun while measuring the surface reflectance every 3 m. Each 90 m line captured 30 measurements, and another 48 points were taken randomly between the lines. After each line, a white reference measurement was taken to compensate for any changes in sun elevation or possible changes in the optical depth during the measurements. All measurements in the area took about 45 min. In total, the BF measurements consisted of 138 points (Fig. 5).

After the BF session, we remeasured the area with the SP using the same $90 \text{ m} \times 90 \text{ m}$ test area, though without any geometry limitations. During the measurements, cumulus and cirrus clouds appeared, but we continued measuring. In total, we measured 70 points with the SP, and it took approximately 20 min. No intercalibration with a white reference was conducted during the measurement session. The white reference at

Fig. 5. Amiaz plain field test site, 90 m × 90 m. Three straight 90 m lines were measured with an additional 48 randomly measured points between these lines (sun elevation 70.54°, sun azimuth 152.13°).

the end of the session was measured and compared to the first white reference, demonstrating maintenance of stability with similar unit values for both.

Fig. 6 shows the spectra of the BF under the EnMAP protocol and the SP measurements, along with the standard deviation (SD) calculated from all of the spectra. The SP provided more stable spectra with SD = 0.38 compared to BF, with SD = 0.46. In addition, the SP provided information across the entire spectral range, including the well-defined spectral region of the atmospheric water vapor attenuation range around 1400 and 1900 nm.

Fig. 7 shows a comparison of the measurements obtained using the BF and SP in August 2022 versus 2021 (1 year apart) at the exact same location in the Amiaz plain. The average spectra showed significant variation for the BF compared to the SP measurements. It should be noted that the two sets of data were acquired by different ASD spectrometers (FieldSpec3 in 2021 and FieldPro4 in 2022). The ASDS values between the average spectrum in each year for both SP and BF were calculated, (0.14 and 0.83, respectively). As a lower ASDS value suggests a closer similarity between two spectra, this indicates that the SP provided better results than the traditional BF measurement. Moreover, the SP enabled compensating not only for the atmospheric variation but also for different spectrometer models. It should be noted that internal calibration for cross-calibration between two or more sensors is an important approach that has not yet been consolidated; these results thus call for more studies on cross-calibration between both ground and orbital sensors. Fig. 8 shows photos from the BF field measurements compared to SP and white reference measurements.

3.3. Case study 3: Proximal sensing of soil water repellency in a field

Water-repellent soils refer to soils that are not readily wetted (also termed hydrophobic). Soil hydrophobicity affects the soil's physical and hydrological properties. It increases hysteresis of the water-retention curve (Ritsema et al., 1998; Bauters et al., 2000), generates unstable wetting fronts due to fingered flow (Hendrickx et al., 1993), reduces infiltration capacity relative to wettable soils (e.g., Wang et al., 2003; Doerr et al., 2006), and induces greater surface runoff and erosion (Burch et al., 1989; Benavides-Solorio and MacDonald, 2001). Soil water repellency (SWR) depends, among other factors, on water content and quality, and soil surface characteristics.

The degree of SWR is commonly quantified by the water drop penetration time (WDPT) test (Doerr, 1998). This method consists of

placing a drop of distilled water on the soil surface and recording the time taken for the drop to penetrate completely into the soil. The intensity of the repellency is usually determined by approximating the surface tension required to initiate infiltration instantly (Letey et al., 2000), a measure of how strongly a soil repels a water drop at the time of application (i.e., how much of the water drop “balls up” on the surface). Whereas both methods can be carried out in the laboratory and in the field, they have the disadvantage of being semi-objective, time-consuming, and requiring expert users and sophisticated techniques (e.g., a well-aligned high-speed video camera). SWR can be strongly altered by variations in environmental conditions, such as humidity (Jex et al., 1985), temperature (Diehl and Schaumann, 2007), moisture content (Täumer et al., 2005), organic matter content and species, and the thin soil layer's structural characteristics; where the measurement must be applied on undisturbed samples under field conditions. Wallach et al. (2005) reported strong development of water repellency in sandy soil under orchard trees that were irrigated with secondary-treated wastewater for 30 years, resulting in the accumulation of hydrophobic organic compounds on the soil surface.

Recent studies have shown that soil spectroscopy in the VIS–NIR–SWIR region (350–2500 nm) has the potential to predict SWR indices. Such studies have been performed in the laboratory with disturbed soil samples of different orders from New Zealand (Kim et al., 2014), and for homogeneous soils from Denmark (Knadel et al., 2016). To the best of our knowledge, assessing hydrophobicity indices, such as WDPT, by VIS–NIR–SWIR reflectance spectroscopy in the field under real conditions on an undisturbed soil surface has never been carried out. The aim of this case study was to use the SP to better measure the reflectance of the undisturbed soil surface, at laboratory quality, in order to extract more reliable field SWR values than is traditionally done.

We therefore conducted the following exercise using the SP assembly to measure the undisturbed soil surface with a parallel measurement of WDPT. Two sets of samples were taken from a 50-year-old orchard plot that had been irrigated with secondary-treated effluent water for 30 years (Wallach et al., 2005): 146 samples were taken to the laboratory under “undisturbed” surface sampling (Persson and Bergström, 1991) and subjected to spectral measurements using the ASD CP assembly in the laboratory and WDPT measurements according to a laboratory protocol (see later); 68 samples were spectrally measured in the field using the SP before the “undisturbed” soil-sampling procedure. These samples were also subjected to WDPT measurements following the same laboratory protocol.

SoilPRO VS. Bare Fiber

Fig. 6. Comparison of representative reflectance and variation over the Amiaz plain area using the bare fiber and the SoilPRO measurements for a 90 m × 90 m test area.

The laboratory protocol for the WDPT measurement consists of placing three 50 mL drops of distilled water on the surface of a soil sample, and determining the time elapsed to the drop’s complete absorption (Doerr, 1998). The time was measured using a high-speed

camera that followed the water drop angle. The spectral measurement was performed for both sets of samples with the same ASD spectrometer, which was hooked up to the CP (in the laboratory set) and the SP (in the field set). The orchard tree area and the sampling locations of all soils for

Fig. 7. Comparison of bare fiber and SoilPRO® reflectance measurements (average of all measurements) over the 90 m × 90 m test area in Amiaz plain in 2021 (solid line) vs. 2022 (dashed line).

Fig. 8. Field measurements using bare fiber (a) compared to SoilPRO (b), and white reference measurements using the SoilPRO (c).

Fig. 9. The exact locations and the WDPT values (in second) that measured in the orchard area.

WDPT measurements are shown in Fig. 9. Most of the sampling points were in shaded areas, without the direct solar radiation needed for ordinary field spectral measurements.

Fig. 10 shows the spectra of some selected soil samples acquired in the field by the SP. The WDPT values for each of the soils are also given. The spectra are very stable, similar to laboratory quality. Especially noticeable is the concave slope across the VIS–NIR–SWIR region that suggests the presence of soil organic carbon (SOC) in both samples (#69 and #64) with the highest WDPT values (502 and 2215, respectively). This is in good agreement with Wallach et al.'s (2005) finding that in this area, the hydrophobic organic substances in the effluent water that have accumulated over the long irrigation period are the driving force

Fig. 10. Spectra of soil samples from the orchard as taken by the SP.

Table 2

The best results of the PLSR model for the validation set using the CP and SP apparatus and the preprocessing method of the reflectance value.

CP data set (n = 146 total; calibration; n = 108, validation n = 38)						
Spectra	R ²	RMSE	RPIQ	Bias	Slope	Factors
Reflectance	0.52	0.73	2.16	-0.24	0.46	7
SP data set (n = 68 total; calibration; n = 51, validation; validation n = 17)						
Spectra	R ²	RMSE	RPIQ	Bias	Slope	Factors
Reflectance *SNV	0.86	0.51	4.43	-1.39	0.91	1

RMSE, root mean square error of prediction; RPIQ, ratio of performance to interquartile distance; SNV, standard normal variate.

for the water repellency characteristics of the soil surface.

The proximate spectral-based model was run on both data sets: 146 samples (calibration n = 108, validation n = 38) with the CP measurement in the laboratory and 68 samples (calibration n = 51, validation n = 17) with the SP measurement in the field. To quantitatively predict the WDPT values by spectroscopy, we ran a partial least squares regression (PLSR) procedure using several preprocessing stages on the reflectance values and their combinations: first derivative, Log (1/R), standard normal variate (SNV) (Dhanoa et al., 1989) and continuum removal (CR) using the PARACUDA-II engine (Gholizadeh et al., 2018) (Table 2). The SP data set (in-situ SP measurements with reflectance SNV preprocessing) gave the best validation results for the PLSR analyses, providing higher accuracy than the CP data set (with reflectance preprocessing) from the laboratory (R² = 0.86 and 0.52, and RPIQ = 4.43 and 2.16, respectively). Although the samples that were brought to the laboratory were kept “undisturbed”, using the CP for the measurement process may have destroyed the fragile soil seal and thus, could not mimic the real in-situ field condition as achieved by the SP measurement. The results demonstrated the potential of the SP assembly for measuring a thin undisturbed soil surface in the field by covering a large representative area with constant geometry and not contacting the soil seal.

In this case study, the SP assembly enabled large-scale, precise and representative spectral measurements of the real undisturbed soil surface with no need to bring the soil to the laboratory. In addition, the SP makes it possible to measure the soil in the field in shaded areas under the tree plant canopy. The SP preserves the soil surface’s condition as it is in the field and therefore provides better proximal spectral modeling to estimate the SWR status. Easy operation of the SP, which does not require skilled personnel, and the ability to measure a large number of samples in a short time (100 samples’ spectra measured in about 60 min) and in shaded areas, place this assembly as a game-changer in assessing the hydrophobicity status of soils beneath tree canopies and close to the irrigation pivot of the drip irrigation practice.

3.4. Case study 4: Assessing the rate of water infiltration into soil profile

This section is a summary of comprehensive research that has been published in the literature between 2021 and 2022. This work has adopted the SP to measure the soil surface condition and its effect on the water regime. In the previous sections, it was demonstrated that the SP gives a better representation of the upper (thin) soil surface layer (“seal”) condition in the field and enables better proximal sensing of soil surface-related properties (e.g., WIR). As the upper layer may be fragile and sensitive to small spectral changes in the field such as fire (Argentero et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2021) or rain energy (Goldshleger et al.,

2009; Li et al., 2020), we further examined the SP’s performance with another surface-related property—water-infiltration rate (WIR).

WIR is a very important hydrological parameter that controls runoff, surface leaching, soil erosion, water-storage capacity in the soil profile, and water availability for crops (Franzluebbers, 2002). Moreover, WIR is involved in several soil processes and has been correlated with vegetation cover (Walker et al., 1981; Thurow et al., 1986, 1988; Van de Koppel et al., 1997, Van de Koppel et al., 2002). Accordingly, WIR may be a critical soil property in combating the desertification phenomenon in the current era of global warming, concomitant with high rain energy and increases in precipitation volume.

WIR into the soil is strongly related to the soil’s surface properties, such as clay minerals, which are not necessarily driven by SOC, as demonstrated with the water repellency issue (SOC may vary from one source to the next and may change the WIR in opposite directions). The WIR is strongly dependent on the interface between the soil and the atmosphere and is mainly controlled by the thin seal that evolves between these two phases (also termed “physical crust” by Agassi et al., 1985, Agassi et al., 1994). Lado et al. (2004) stated that an increase in SOC limits soil seal formation and therefore may induce infiltration. On the other hand, in some cases (e.g., case study 3 in this paper and supported by Capriel, 1997), some species of SOC may cause hydrophobicity and thus decrease the WIR values. Ben-Hur and Letey (1989) found that clay dispersion at the soil surface determines WIR and affects seal formation. Stern et al. (1991) examined the relationship between clay minerals and WIR status and found that soils rich in smectite minerals are more vulnerable to sealing and erosion. They suggested that kaolinite and illite have opposite effects on soil sealing and the resulting erosion. Goldshleger et al. (2009) predicted WIR via spectroscopy and PLSR analyses in disturbed soils under a controlled rain simulator using varying raindrop energy. As the soil under the rain simulator did not mimic the real in-situ field condition (the soil surface was disturbed when it was brought to the laboratory), the rain simulator showed only trends, and not the actual field condition. As a result, the real field WIR must be examined with a different protocol.

The aim of this case study was to minimize the destructive effect of the traditional CP measurement on the soil crust, and avoid indirect assessment of the WIR in the laboratory. Accordingly, we used the SP assembly to measure the reflectance values of the soil surface in the field while simultaneously measuring WIR with a mini disk infiltrometer (Decagon Devices, Inc). Several samples from different locations across Mediterranean countries that present variations in soil texture were selected: one place in Italy, one place in Israel and three in Greece (Fig. 11). After spectral and WIR measurements in the field, the soil samples were brought to the laboratory and the spectral measurements were performed on a disturbed mixed soil sample, using Ben Dor et al.’s (2015) protocol for laboratory ASD spectrometer measurements with the CP assembly.

To generate the spectral-based models for the WIR prediction, the spectral data were subjected to several preprocessing techniques. The spectral readings in the field (using the SP) and the laboratory (using the CP) were compared to the WIR measured in the field. Table 3 provides the results of the validation stage for both spectral measurement practices after Savitzky–Golay and first-derivative preprocessing approaches were executed, and the PLSR models were generated. The mixed data set (generic) showed excellent results in the field domain using the SP (R²_{val} = 0.70). Although the validation of the laboratory-based model also showed an acceptable performance (R²_{val} = 0.57). These results

Fig. 11. The areas where the samples were first measured by the SoilPRO® (SP) in the field and then collected to be brought to the laboratory (Israel, Greece and Southern Italy).

Table 3

The generic soil samples as divided by country and texture to arrange them into sand and clay groups.

Field	Country	No. of samples	Classification	Texture group
Sde Yoav	Israel	30	Clay loam	Heavily clayed
Afeka	Israel	18	Sandy clay loam	Heavily clayed
Alento	Italy	21	Loam	Heavily clayed
C. Macedonia 1	Greece	16	Sand	Sandy light
C. Macedonia 2	Greece	15	Sandy loam	Sandy light
C. Macedonia 3	Greece	14	Sandy loam	Sandy light

indicated that the field spectral data are more effective for predicting WIR, where the soil seal is not destroyed, and the surface is not disturbed. The beta coefficients of the field- and laboratory-based models were assessed to analyze the main chromophores that enable accurate WIR prediction. As it was assumed that WIR is strongly affected by soil texture, we split the data set (generic) into sandy and clayey groups (Table 3).

For the sand group, a model was developed using the PLSR model after the spectral data were transformed into apparent absorbance, and then Savitzky–Golay and first derivative was conducted. For the models, we used five components. As seen in Table 4, similar to the generic group, the field-based sand model, developed using SP spectra, showed a better and higher correlation than the laboratory-based sand model, developed using CP spectra, ($R_{val}^2 = 0.82$ and 0.22 , respectively).

For the clay group, the spectral data were first preprocessed using the Savitzky–Golay and first derivative, and six components that performed best in the field were used to calibrate the models. Following Francos and Ben-Dor (2022), the laboratory model was extracted using analytical approach similar to those for the field condition according to protocol. As seen in Table 4, both field- and laboratory-based models presented excellent validation using the full spectral range (VIS–NIR–SWIR) ($R_{val}^2 = 0.81$, $R_{val}^2 = 0.70$, respectively) but similarly, as demonstrated in the sand and generic groups, the field-based models yielded better results.

Fig. 12 shows the beta coefficients that represent the wavelengths' importance for all groups under field and laboratory conditions. Except for the generic group in the laboratory, all other groups, in both field and laboratory, emphasized the VIS–NIR spectral region based on the presence of iron oxides and organic matter. It is apparent that this region is more spectrally pronounced in the field than in the laboratory. As these regions are highly assigned to free iron oxides and organic matter substances, it seems that these two attributes are better detected as part of a physical crust enriched with these constituents. In the SWIR region, and especially in the sand group, the features of clay minerals at 2200 nm were more enhanced, whereas this was not so in the clay group. This is explained by the fact that clay is a marginal part of the physical crust, it is more pronounced on the sand background, than on clay. This is also reflected in the higher accuracy of the field model compared to the laboratory model ($R_{val}^2 = 0.82$ and 0.22 , respectively). For the generic group, it is apparent that in the field, the spectral assignments are more enhanced relative to the laboratory conditions. It is also clear that the

Table 4

The statistics calculated for the validation samples in the (a) generic, (b) clay and (c) sand groups in the laboratory vs. field domain.

Generic (a)		
Parameters	Field (SP)	Laboratory (CP)
$RPIQ_{Cal}$	10.83	5.26
$R2_{Cal}$	0.98	0.92
$RMSE_{Cal}$	0.0001	0.0002
No. of samples _{Cal}	83	83
$RPIQ_{Val}$	2.26	1.87
$R2_{Val}$	0.71	0.57
$RMSE_{Val}$	0.0004	0.0004
No. of samples _{Val}	21	21
P -value _{Val}	0	0.0001
No. of components	9	9
Preprocessing	1st derivative	1st derivative
Clay (b)		
Parameters	Field (SP)	Laboratory (CP)
$RPIQ_{Cal}$	17.66	4.96
$R2_{Cal}$	0.98	0.89
$RMSE_{Cal}$	0.0001	0.0002
No. of samples _{Cal}	37	37
$RPIQ_{Val}$	3.14	2.85
$R2_{Val}$	0.81	0.70
$RMSE_{Val}$	0.0003	0.0004
No. of samples _{Val}	9	9
P -value _{Val}	0.0004	0.0025
No. of components	6	6
Preprocessing	1st derivative	1st derivative
Sand (c)		
Parameters	Field (SP)	Laboratory (CP)
$RPIQ_{Cal}$	4.24	1.8
$R2_{Cal}$	0.90	0.48
$RMSE_{Cal}$	0.0002	0.22
No. of samples _{Cal}	46	46
$RPIQ_{Val}$	3.19	1.18
$R2_{Val}$	0.82	0.22
$RMSE_{Val}$	0.0004	0.0007
No. of samples _{Val}	12	12
P -value _{Val}	0.0001	0.123
No. of components	5	5
Preprocessing	Absorbance & 1st derivative	Absorbance & 1st derivative

water in the generic group is important, similar to the clay group (around 1900 nm), which suggests that the clay fraction in both generic and clay groups is responsible for the adsorbed water molecules. This is based on the high specific surface area of clay relative to sand (Knadel et al., 2016). Under field conditions (field-dried), the soils are relatively moister than in the laboratory (air-dried), so a significant important spectral signal at around 1900 nm can be seen in both the clay and generic groups.

The results of the WIR exercise reinforced the importance of measuring undisturbed soil surface properties in field, where the SP provides an excellent solution. The thin soil seal strongly controlled the WIR, and the main factor was clay texture, in general, and clay minerals, in particular. In this case, the SP demonstrated its ability to provide real soil surface spectra under real field conditions characterized by very high spectral quality without destroying the fragile soil seal.

Fig. 12. Feature importance as demonstrated by the beta coefficient spectra of the models in the sand, clay and generic groups in the field (with SP) and the laboratory (with CP).

3.5. Case study 5: Soil surface measurements under extremely low solar angle over the South Shetland Islands, Antarctica

Antarctica’s high latitude means that sunlight (insolation) hits the surface at a low angle (low angle of incidence). Southwards of the Antarctic Circle (66.56°S), there is a period during the austral summer

when the sun does not set below the horizon (the length of this period increases with increasing latitude). At the South Pole, there is continuously low-angle sunlight between 21 September and 21 March, and darkness during the other half of the year. However, not all of Antarctica is below the Antarctic Circle, which is the demarcation line for the 24-h summer days. Much of the peninsula and its coastal islands are north of

Fig. 13. The study areas and location of the sampling sites (a) in Antarctica and (b) within the South Shetland Islands.

Table 5
Spectral measurements of bare soils taken at different locations.

Site	Date (dd/mm/yy)	Latitude	Longitude	Elevation (m a.s.l.) ¹⁾	Measurement starting time	Measurement ending time	Solar zenith start	Solar zenith end
LIBP	04/02/22	62.665°S	61.104°W	14	10:13	11:02	56.54°	52.26°
LIHP	14/02/22	62.664°S	60.388°W	15	11:01	12:17	55.19°	50.87°
KGFP	08/03/22	62.179°S	58.925°W	47	17:02	17:41	71.84°	76.06°

¹⁾m a.s.l., meters above sea level.

Fig. 14. Bare soil surface covers (a) on Fildes Peninsula (KGFP), (b) a corresponding 1 m² subplot on KGFP, (c) Byers Peninsula (LIBP) and (d) taking spectral measurements with the SP apparatus.

Table 6
Surrounding geomorphology and surface characteristic of the different sites.

Site	Topography	Slope (%)	Land form	Parent material	Clast coverage (%)	Coarse (>2 mm)	Texture class
LIBP	Undulating	0–0.1	Holocene raised beach	Colluvium	15	16.8	Loamy sand
LIHP	Hilly	0.1–2	Floodplain	Alluvium	50	28.1	Sand
KGFP	Hilly	0.1–2	Terrace	Colluvium	40	43	Sand

the Circle where the solar angle during the austral summer is higher. This is the ideal location to acquire spectral field measurements across the VIS–NIR–SWIR (350–2500 nm) region, when the sun is highest in the sky, to minimize the effects of shadowing and solar zenith changes, and within the range of 2 h on either side of solar noon (Rollin et al., 2000; Pfitzner et al., 2011; Schweiger, 2020). However, weather conditions in the Northern Antarctic Peninsula region often influence fieldwork and especially spectroscopy, when measuring soil surface reflectance. In exceptional cases, it has been possible to simultaneously obtain field spectral and satellite data (Schmid et al., 2021). This case study's areas (Fig. 13) are in the South Shetland Islands, which are characterized by a maritime Antarctic climate. The mean annual air temperature is -2.2°C and there is between 350 and 1000 mm of precipitation per year (Simas et al., 2015). There is a high percentage of cloud cover (annual mean cloud cover is approximately 80%) due to water vapor abundance and the high frequency of cyclones passing over the region (Bañón et al., 2013).

This case study was conducted within the framework of Spanish R&D to develop the Northern Antarctic Spectral Library (NAPSPEC). The aim was to examine the SP's performance in extracting reliable soil spectral information across the whole spectral range (including over the water vapor absorption wavelengths under the aforementioned extreme conditions. Reference spectra for field conditions were obtained during a field campaign in 2022 to characterize bare soil surfaces in ice-free areas of the South Shetland Islands. Different locations (Fig. 13) were visited on Byers Peninsula and Hurd Peninsula of Livingston Island, and Fildes Peninsula of King George Island.

A selection of spectra (Table 5) was chosen from the NAPSPEC

library during the campaign that were measured during the austral summer, representing bare soil surfaces. The spectral measurements of the bare soils were taken on Byers Peninsula (LIBP) and Hurd Peninsula (LIHP) in February, and on Fildes Peninsula (KGFP) at the beginning of March.

The seasonal variation in solar zenith angle (SZA) from 1 July 2021 to 30 June 2022 reached its lowest value (38.76°) at 13:00 h on 21 December 2021 for the study site at KGFP. The SZA at noon for LIBP on 4 February 2022, for LIHP on 14 February 2022 and for KGFP on 8 March 2022 was 46.58° , 49.80° and 54.22° , respectively. These are high SZA values, which are equivalent to low sun angles. Coinciding with a reasonable optimum SZA is complicated due to the bad meteorological conditions and logistical demands in an area such as Antarctica.

Field spectroradiometry was carried out for selected field plots (Fig. 14) consisting of bare soils using an ASD FieldSpec3 full spectral range instrument (350 to 2500 nm) together with the SP apparatus with an artificial light source and when weather permitted, a BF using sunlight, mounted in a pistol grip.

The SP apparatus was used at all sites, whereas it was only possible to use the BF for a limited time at LIHP. Bare soil surface covers were selected with an area of at least 900 m² and a total of 7 subplots of 1 m² (Fig. 14b) to obtain 5 spectral measurements in each subplot. Therefore, a total of 35 spectral curves were obtained to represent each area using the SP. In the case of the spectra obtained at LIHP using the BF inserted into the handheld pistol grip, only 2 subplots were obtained.

The plots were located on different landforms surrounded by undulating or hilly topography (Table 6). In this climate, cryoclastic weathering is predominant due to frequent freeze–thaw cycles breaking down

Fig. 15. Average spectra obtained with the SP apparatus for different subplots of bare soil surface covers representing (a) Byers Peninsula (LIBP), (b) Hurd Peninsula (LIHP), and (c) Fildes Peninsula (KGFP). (d) Comparison with spectra obtained with the bare optical fiber for LIHP.

the rocks into clasts of all sizes. The exposed bare soil surfaces are generally unstable, affected by water and wind erosion. The latter has the effect of moving the fine soil particles and leaving the clasts exposed on the soil surface. The soil texture classes are loamy sand and sand with an important percentage of coarse fraction.

The soils found at these sites are poorly developed because conditions for soil formation are limited to the short austral summer, when temperatures oscillate around 0 °C. These soils are closely related to the parent material. The colluvium of LIBP is made up of basaltic and silicic pyroclastic material (López-Martínez et al., 1996), and the soil is slightly acidic with a pH of 5.8; the alluvium of LIHP is made up of glaciofluvial till from sedimentary rocks consisting of shales and graywackes (Smellie et al., 1984) with a near-neutral pH of 6.8, and the colluvium of KGFP consists of weathered materials from agglomerates and basaltic lavas (Smellie et al., 1984) with a neutral pH of 7.0. The soils have a low organic matter content (0.1–0.3%) and a free iron oxide content of 0.7, 1.4 and 2.4% for LIHP, KGFP, and LIBP, respectively. The KGFP soil is at 47 m above sea level and under the influence of permafrost in the ground that is within a depth of less than 1 m. The spectra obtained for the different plots under field conditions using the SP apparatus (Fig. 15) represented common soil surfaces within the ice-free areas that are the result of physically weathered material.

Non-homogeneities from one subplot to another resulted in

dispersion of the spectral curves at each location although they maintained their overall form. This can be seen in Fig. 15a and b and to a lesser extent in Fig. 15c. However, the spectra were consistent for the individual areas and the advantage is that they were normally taken under extensive cloud cover with no concern for time of day with optimal SZA, and at the end of the austral summer, when days are notably shorter. The spectral comparison between measurements obtained with the optical BF and the SP (Fig. 15d) shows that the latter were more stable, especially in the SWIR range. Moreover, the reflectance was notably higher and attributed to the relatively high SZA. The atmospheric conditions with high humidity content influenced the measurements; in this case, only 10 measurements were taken with the BF due to the unstable meteorological conditions.

In general, the advantages of using the SP in high-latitude regions are numerous and greatly improve the spectral quality within the VIS, NIR and SWIR range under field conditions. As mentioned earlier, the FOV of the apparatus makes it possible to obtain representative spectra of a bare soil cover despite some surface roughness due to rocks and aggregates. In remote places such as Antarctica, access to any region is limited and often depends on multiple factors. Therefore, reliable equipment is needed to obtain stable spectral data without excessive delays.

4. Discussion

The SP enables accurate predictions of soil surface-related properties, mimicking the exact soil surface condition. It provides reflectance of the undisturbed soil surface using any portable spectrometer equipped with fiber optics, which can be operated by any user (expert or non-expert). The current study investigated the discrepancies between field and laboratory spectral observations, which are especially important for soil surface-dependent properties such as WIR and SWR, and for reflectance measurements in the field under a standard and stable protocol that can be used by any non-skilled user. The SP's potential to derive high-quality reflectance data in the field under extreme conditions (e.g., low sun elevation angle, shaded areas, cloudy areas) and at an exact time (e.g., during VC) suggests that this apparatus may be a game-changer for the field soil spectroscopy arena. This is based on other methods that require time and infrastructure (e.g., field goniometer), whereas the ordinary methods (e.g., CP or BF) suffer from being non-representative of, or insensitive to, small environmental changes. The SP provides laboratory-quality data that are more reliable than those obtained in the laboratory to describe the soil surface condition *in situ*.

Many soil surface-related properties need to be assessed (both spectrally and chemically) under undisturbed and extreme conditions, and the SP demonstrates an elegant and a simple way to execute such measurements. Furthermore, as the SP-acquired field measurements are of laboratory quality, it may be possible to find a transfer function between the two sets of measurements. This is essential to scale up all laboratory SSLs to a surface view, as seen by remote sensors. With that in mind, [Francos and Ben-Dor \(2022\)](#) demonstrated the possibility of finding a transfer function between a local laboratory SSL and field SSL for a selected group of soils. We suggest that to further the laboratory SSL, a field SSL be generated using the SP. Because more soils will be measured twice—in the field and in the laboratory—transfer functions will be generated for more soil types, and not only for a local SSL. This may harmonize the laboratory and field measurements toward implementing the data and the extracted models for remote-sensing domains (field SSL). Thus, from the five presented case studies, and from the fact that remote sensors scan the upper soil layer, transfer functions may be a way to exploit the many existing laboratory SSLs. In general, it should be highlighted that monitoring the surface soil under real field conditions (e.g., sealed or hydrophobic) requires a new and innovative approach, which the SP provides.

The many advantages of the SP, aside from measuring the soil surface without disturbing it, include the following: many samples can be measured in the field within a short time while maintaining laboratory quality and CP geometry; it has a fixed geometry that enables retaining reproducibility, regardless of the skill of the user; it can be hooked to any portable spectrometer with a fiber-optic cable; it provides a full spectrum across the VIS–NIR–SWIR region; it can measure the soil surface at any time of the day or night, as well as in the shade; it preserves a clean white reference relative to CP or BF practices; it is easy to use and is not sensitive to atmospheric attenuation or sun angle variations. The disadvantages of the SP are as follows: due to the fixed geometry, it does not account for the sun's elevation, so it may be biased with severe non-Lambertian surfaces or in the presence of large irregular aggregates; areas with excessive moisture saturation may cause the formation of water vapor inside the SP space due to evaporation caused by the warming effect of the lamp—this may hinder estimations of high water content in the soil, but this issue is still being investigated. The roughness issue can be assessed by a 2D stereo camera and harmonization of field SSLs by adopting an internal standard approach as used in laboratory SSL practice. Taken together, the advantages of the SP far outweigh its disadvantages—many of which may be solved with the upcoming new version of the SP.

Although we presented only five case studies to demonstrate the SP's performance, it is highly expected that more applications will be

developed based on the SP and near Lambertian surfaces (e.g., asphalt concrete assessment). Its simplicity and stability during the measurements, and the fact that skilled personnel are not required, make the SP a unique tool for field spectroscopy practices and may advance those practices to build and harmonize field SSLs. It can also be used for cross-calibration between portable field sensors that are far away from each other. We are expecting to uncover more applications for the SP while applying them to routine field spectral measurements, and we encourage users to adopt this strategy to measure soil surfaces in the field with either the SP or a similar assembly.

5. Summary and conclusion

The current study tested the capability of the SP apparatus in five case studies. The first demonstrated its ability to acquire reflectance measurements under any atmospheric conditions, at any time of the day. The second showed its ability to acquire reflectance information during VC of HSR satellite sensors, where many readings over a uniform playa demonstrated less variation than the traditional BF measurements. In addition, the entire set of measurements was acquired in a relatively short time, which is important during a sensor's overpass. In the third study, we highlighted the improved prediction of SWR using SP measurements. This property is strongly dependent on soil surface properties, which were governed by organic substances in our case. This example also showed the SP's ability to work in shaded areas with high spectral quality. The fourth case study also demonstrated a precise way of measuring the soil surface characteristics that control WIR into the soil profile at the pedosphere–atmosphere interface. The SP measurements provided a better prediction model for WIR than relying on measurements taken in the laboratory with disturbed soils. Finally, the fifth example presented the SP's potential for outdoor work under very low sun elevation. The reflectance spectra could be acquired in the field with laboratory quality at the South Pole. In this area, there is no other concrete way to measure the soil surface in a representative fashion (i.e., a large and preserved surface area). Therefore, it is concluded that the SP assembly is a game-changer for the spectral measurement of soils under field conditions, as well as under unstable and less-than optimal atmospheric conditions and illumination status. It enables mimicking the exact soil surface conditions with laboratory quality. All in all, this paper may be considered a precursor to other applications that require field reflectance data with high reproducibility and high quality.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Eyal Ben-Dor reports a relationship with Tel Aviv University that includes: employment and travel reimbursement. Eyal Ben-Dor has patent #U.S. Patent Office Serial No. 15407295 licensed to yes.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

This work was conducted within the Probe Field project funded in the framework of the Horizon 2020 European Joint Program for SOIL. This work was also partially supported by Project N080341031 of the Lowy International School at Tel Aviv University and Projects RTI2018-098099-B-I00 and PID2021-125778OB-I00 of the Spanish R&D National Plan, financed by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation.

References

- Agassi, M., Morin, J., Shainberg, I., 1985. Effect of raindrop impact energy and water salinity on infiltration rates of sodic soils. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 49, 186–190. <https://doi.org/10.2136/SSSAJ1985.03615995004900010037X>.
- Agassi, M., Bloem, D., Ben-Hur, M., 1994. Effect of drop energy and soil and water chemistry on infiltration and erosion. *Water Resour. Res.* 30, 1187–1193. <https://doi.org/10.1029/93WR02880>.
- Argentiero, I., Ricci, G.F., Elia, M., D'este, M., Giannico, V., Ronco, F.V., Gentile, F., Sanesi, G., 2021. Combining methods to estimate post-fire soil erosion using remote sensing data. *Forests* 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f12081105>.
- Bañón, M., Justel, A., Velázquez, D., Quesada, A., 2013. Regional weather survey on Byers Peninsula, Livingston Island, South Shetland Islands, Antarctica. *Antarctic Sci.* 25, 146–156. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0954102012001046>.
- Bauters, T.W.J., Dicarolo, D.A., Steenhuis, T.S., Parlange, J.Y., 2000. Soil water content dependent wetting front characteristics in sands. *J. Hydrol.* 231–232, 244–254. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694\(00\)00198-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694(00)00198-0).
- Behera, S.K., Adamchuk, V.I., Shukla, A.K., Pandey, P.S., Kumar, P., Shukla, V., Thiyagarajan, C., Rai, H.K., Hadole, S., Sachan, A.K., Singh, P., Trivedi, V., Mishra, A., Butail, N.P., Kumar, P., Prapajati, R., Tiwari, K., Suri, D., Sharma, M., 2022. The scope for using proximal soil sensing by the farmers of India. *Sustainability* 14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14148561>.
- Ben Dor, E., Ong, C., Lau, I.C., 2015. Reflectance measurements of soils in the laboratory: standards and protocols. *Geoderma* 245–246, 112–124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2015.01.002>.
- Benavides-Solorio, J., MacDonald, L.H., 2001. Post-fire runoff and erosion from simulated rainfall on small plots, Colorado Front Range. *Hydrol. Process.* 15, 2931–2952. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.383>.
- Ben-Dor, E., Banin, A., 1995. Near-infrared analysis as a rapid method to simultaneously evaluate several soil properties. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 59, 364–372. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1995.03615995005900020014x>.
- Ben-Dor, E., Granot, A., Notesco, G., 2017. A simple apparatus to measure soil spectral information in the field under stable conditions. *Geoderma* 306, 73–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2017.06.025>.
- Ben-Hur, M., Letey, J., 1989. Effect of polysaccharides, clay dispersion, and impact energy on water infiltration. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 53, 233–238. <https://doi.org/10.2136/SSSAJ1989.03615995005300010041X>.
- Bouvet, M., Thome, K., Berthelot, B., Bialek, A., Czaplá-Myers, J., Fox, N.P., Goryl, P., Henry, P., Ma, L., Marq, S., Meygret, A., Wenny, B.N., Woolliams, E.R., 2019. RadCalNet: a radiometric calibration network for earth observing imagers operating in the visible to shortwave infrared spectral range. *Remote Sens.* 11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11202401>.
- Burch, G.J., Moore, L.D., Burns, J., 1989. Soil hydrophobic effects on infiltration and catchment runoff. *Hydrol. Process.* 3, 211–222. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.3360030302>.
- Capriel, P., 1997. Hydrophobicity of organic matter in arable soils: influence of management. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 48, 457–462. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2389.1997.tb00211.x>.
- Christy, C.D., 2008. Real-time measurement of soil attributes using on-the-go near infrared reflectance spectroscopy. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* 61, 10–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2007.02.010>.
- Dhanoa, M.S., Lister, S.J., Barnes, R.J., 1989. Standard normal variate transformation and de-trending of near-infrared diffuse reflectance spectra. *Appl. Spectrosc.* 43, 772–777.
- Diehl, D., Schaumann, G.E., 2007. The nature of wetting on urban soil samples: wetting kinetics and evaporation assessed from sessile drop shape. *Hydrol. Process.* 21, 2255–2265. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.6745>.
- Doerr, S.H., 1998. On standardizing the “water drop penetration time” and the “molarity of an ethanol droplet” techniques to classify soil hydrophobicity: a case study using medium textured soils. *Earth Surf. Process. Landforms* 23, 663–668. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1096-9837\(199807\)23:7<663::AID-ESP909>3.0.CO;2-6](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1096-9837(199807)23:7<663::AID-ESP909>3.0.CO;2-6).
- Doerr, S.H., Shakesby, R.A., Dekker, L.W., Ritsema, C.J., 2006. Occurrence, prediction and hydrological effects of water repellency amongst major soil and land-use types in a humid temperate climate. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 57, 741–754. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2389.2006.00818.x>.
- Franco, N., Romano, N., Nasta, P., Zeng, Y., Szabó, B., Manfreda, S., Ciraolo, G., Mészáros, J., Zhuang, R., Su, B., Ben-Dor, E., 2021. Mapping water infiltration rate using ground and uav hyperspectral data: A case study of alento, italy. *Remote Sens.* 13, 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13132606>.
- Franzluebbers, A.J., 2002. Water infiltration and soil structure related to organic matter and its stratification with depth. *Soil Tillage Res.* 66, 197–205. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987\(02\)00027-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987(02)00027-2).
- Gholizadeh, A., Saberioon, M., Carmon, N., Boruvka, L., Ben-Dor, E., 2018. Examining the performance of PARACUDA-II data-mining engine versus selected techniques to model soil carbon from reflectance spectra. *Remote Sens.* 10. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs10081172>.
- Goldshleger, N., Ben-Dor, E., Chudnovsky, A., Agassi, M., 2009. Soil reflectance as a generic tool for assessing infiltration rate induced by structural crust for heterogeneous soils. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 60, 1038–1051. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2389.2009.01162.x>.
- Gomez, C., Viscarra Rossel, R.A., McBratney, A.B., 2008. Soil organic carbon prediction by hyperspectral remote sensing and field vis-NIR spectroscopy: An Australian case study. *Geoderma* 146, 403–411. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2008.06.011>.
- Heller-Pearlshtien, D., Ben-Dor, E., 2022. CalVal Evaluation of DESIS products in Amiaz Plain and Makhtesh Ramon Test sites, in: 1st DESIS User Workshop – Imaging Spectrometer Space Mission, Calibration and Validation, Applications, Methods, 28 Sept.–1 Oct. 2021, Virtual. The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences, pp. 13–21.
- Heller-Pearlshtien, D., Pignatti, S., Greisman-Ran, U., Ben-Dor, E., 2021. PRISMA sensor evaluation: a case study of mineral mapping performance over Makhtesh Ramon. *Israel. Int. J. Remote Sens.* 42, 5882–5914.
- Heller-Pearlshtien, D., Pignatti, S., Ben-Dor, E., 2023. Vicarious CAL/VAL approach for orbital hyperspectral sensors using multiple sites. *Remote Sens.* 15, 771. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15030771>.
- Hendrickx, J.M.H., Dekker, L.W., Boersma, O.H., 1993. Unstable wetting fronts in water-repellent field soils. *J. Environ. Qual.* 22, 109–118. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq1993.00472425002200010014x>.
- Jex, G.W., Bleakley, B.H., Hubbell, D.H., Munro, L.L., 1985. High humidity-induced increase in water repellency in some sandy soils. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 49, 1177–1182. <https://doi.org/10.2136/SSSAJ1985.03615995004900050021X>.
- Kim, I., Pullanagari, R.R., Deurer, M., Singh, R., Huh, K.Y., Clothier, B.E., 2014. The use of visible and near-infrared spectroscopy for the analysis of soil water repellency. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 65, 360–368. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12138>.
- Knadell, M., Masis-Meléndez, F., De Jonge, L.W., Moldrup, P., Arthur, E., Greve, M.H., 2016. Assessing soil water repellency of a sandy field with visible near infrared spectroscopy. *J. Near Infrared Spectrosc.* 24, 215–224. <https://doi.org/10.1255/jnirs.1188>.
- Kodaira, M., Shibusawa, S., 2013. Using a mobile real-time soil visible-near infrared sensor for high resolution soil property mapping. *Geoderma* 199, 64–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2012.09.007>.
- Kokaly, R.F., Turpie, K.R., 2019. Calibration and validation working group for surface biology and geology (SBG). In: IGARSS 2019-2019 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium. IEEE, pp. 8517–8518.
- Kusumo, B.H., 2018. In situ measurement of soil carbon with depth using near infrared (NIR) spectroscopy. *IOP Conf. Ser. Mater. Sci. Eng.* 434. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/434/1/012235>.
- Labarre, S., Jacquemoud, S., Ferrari, C., Delorme, A., Derrien, A., Grandin, R., Tanguy, B., 2019. Retrieving soil surface roughness with the Hapke photometric model: Confrontation with the ground truth. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 225, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2019.02.014>.
- Lado, M., Paz, A., Ben-Hur, M., 2004. Organic matter and aggregate-size interactions in saturated hydraulic conductivity. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 68, 234–242. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2004.2340>.
- Letey, J., Carrillo, M.L.K., Pang, X.P., 2000. Approaches to characterize the degree of water repellency. *J. Hydrol.* 231–232, 61–65. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694\(00\)00183-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1694(00)00183-9).
- Li, J., Wang, W., Guo, M., Kang, H., Wang, Z., Huang, J., Sun, B., Wang, K., Zhang, G., Bai, Y., 2020. Effects of soil texture and gravel content on the infiltration and soil loss of spoil heaps under simulated rainfall. *J. Soil. Sediment.* 20, 3896–3908. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11368-020-02729-6>.
- López-Martínez, J., Martínez de Pisón, E., Serrano, E., Arche, A., 1996. Geomorphological map of Byers Peninsula, Livingston Island. *BAS Geomap Series. With Supplementary Text. British Antarctic Survey, Cambridge.*
- Milton, E.J., 2010. Review article: principles of field spectroscopy. *Int. J. Remote Sens.* 8, 1807–1827. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431168708954818>.
- Milton, E.J., Schaeppman, M.E., Anderson, K., Kneubühler, M., Fox, N., 2009. Progress in field spectroscopy. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 113, S92–S109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2007.08.001>.
- Morain, S.A., Budge, A.M., 2004. Post-Launch Calibration of Satellite Sensors. *Post-Launch Calibration of Satellite Sensors*. 10.1201/9780203026830.
- Peddle, D.R., Peter White, H., Soffer, R.J., Miller, J.R., LeDrew, E.F., 2001. Reflectance processing of remote sensing spectroradiometer data. *Comput. Geosci.* 27, 203–213. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0098-3004\(00\)0096-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0098-3004(00)0096-0).
- Persson, L., Bergström, L., 1991. Drilling method for collection of undisturbed soil monoliths. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 55, 285–287. <https://doi.org/10.2136/SSSAJ1991.03615995005500010050X>.
- Pfritzer, K., Bartolo, R., Carr, G., Esparon, A., Bollhöfer, A., 2011. Standards for reflectance spectral measurement of temporal vegetation plots. *Supervising Scientist Report 195. Supervising Scientist, Darwin NT.* ISBN: 978-1-921069-16-1.
- RadCalNet Portal, n.d. <https://www.radcalnet.org/#/> (accessed 22 July 2021).
- Ritsema, C.J., Nieber, J.L., Dekker, L.W., Steenhuis, T.S., 1998. Stable or unstable wetting fronts in water repellent soils – effect of antecedent soil moisture content. *Soil Tillage Res.* 47, 111–123. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987\(98\)00082-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987(98)00082-8).
- Rodionov, A., Welp, G., Damerow, L., Berg, T., Amelung, W., Pätzold, S., 2015. Towards on-the-go field assessment of soil organic carbon using Vis-NIR diffuse reflectance spectroscopy: developing and testing a novel tractor-driven measuring chamber. *Soil Tillage Res.* 145, 93–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2014.08.007>.
- Rollin, E., Milton, E., Emery, D., 2000. Reference panel anisotropy and diffuse radiation – some implications for field spectroscopy. *Int. J. Remote Sens.* 21, 2799–2810. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431160050121258>.
- Schmid, T., Nieto, A., López-Martínez, J., Guillaso, S., Koch, M., Oliva-Urcia, B., Lambán, L.J., 2021. Characterizing the ice-free area of Cierva Point (Antarctic Peninsula) using reflectance spectroscopy. *IGARSS IEEE International* 6178–6181. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS47720.2021.9554835>.
- Schopfer, J.T., 2008. Spectrodirectional ground-based remote sensing using dual-view goniometry. *Field BRF retrieval and assessment of the diffuse irradiance distribution in spectrodirectional field measurements. Remote Sens. Ser.* 53, 93.
- Schweiger, A.K., 2020. Spectral field campaigns: planning and data collection, in: Cavender-Bares, J., Gamon, J.A., Townsend, P.A. (Eds.), *Remote Sensing of Plant Biodiversity*. Springer, Cham, pp. 385–423. 10.1007/978-3-030-33157-3_15.
- Simas, F.N.B., Schaefer, C.E.G.R., Michel, R.F.M., Francelino, M.R., Bockheim, J.G., 2015. Soils of the South Orkney and South Shetland, in: Bockheim, J.G. (Ed.), *The*

- Soils of Antarctica. World Soils Book Series. Springer, Cham, pp. 227–273. 10.1007/978-3-319-05497-1_13.
- Smellie, J.L., Pankhurst, R.J., Thomson, M.R.A., Davies, R.E.S., 1984. The Geology of the South Shetland Islands: VI. Stratigraphy, Geochemistry and Evolution. British Antarctic Survey, Cambridge (British Antarctic Survey Scientific Reports 87).
- Stenberg, B., Viscarra Rossel, R.A., Mouazen, A.M., Wetterlind, J., 2010. Visible and near infrared spectroscopy in soil science. *Adv. Agron.* 107, 163–215. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113\(10\)07005-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113(10)07005-7).
- Stern, R., Ben-Hur, M., Shainberg, I., 1991. Clay mineralogy effect on rain infiltration, seal formation and soil losses. *Soil Sci.* 152, 455–462. <https://agris.fao.org/agris-search/search.do?recordID=US9311511>.
- Stoner, E.R., Baumgardner, M.F., Weismiller, R.A., Biehl, L.L., Robinson, B.F., 1980. Extension of laboratory-measured soil spectra to field conditions. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 44 (3), 572–574. <https://doi.org/10.2136/SSAJ1980.03615995004400030028X>.
- SVC, 2019. Field Spectroscopy Guide with SVC i-series Spectroradiometers 1–76.
- Täumer, K., Stoffregen, H., Wessolek, G., 2005. Determination of repellency distribution using soil organic matter and water content. *Geoderma* 125, 107–115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2004.07.004>.
- Thenkabail, P.S., 2016. Remotely Sensed Data Characterized, Classification and Accuracies. *Remote Sensing Handbook, Volume 1*. Taylor & Francis Group, Oxfordshire.
- Thurow, T.L., Blackburn, W.H., Taylor, C.A., 1986. Hydrologic characteristics of vegetation types as affected by livestock grazing systems, Edwards Plateau, Texas. *J. Range Manag.* 39, 505. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3898758>.
- Thurow, T.L., Blackburn, W.H., Taylor, C.A., 1988. Infiltration and interrill erosion responses to selected livestock grazing strategies, Edwards Plateau, Texas. *J. Range Manag.* 41, 296. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3899382>.
- Van de Koppel, J., Rietkerk, M., Weissing, F.J., 1997. Catastrophic vegetation shifts and soil degradation in terrestrial grazing systems. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 12, 352–356. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347\(97\)01133-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-5347(97)01133-6).
- Van de Koppel, J., Rietkerk, M., Van Langevelde, F., Kumar, L., Klausmeier, C.A., Fryxell, J.M., Hearne, J.W., Van Andel, J., De Ridder, N., Skidmore, A., Stroosnijder, L., Prins, H.H.T., 2002. Spatial heterogeneity and irreversible vegetation change in semiarid grazing systems. *Am. Nat.* 159, 209–218. <https://doi.org/10.1086/324791>.
- Viscarra Rossel, R.A., Walvoort, D.J.J., McBratney, A.B., Janik, L.J., Skjemstad, J.O., 2006. Visible, near infrared, mid infrared or combined diffuse reflectance spectroscopy for simultaneous assessment of various soil properties. *Geoderma* 131, 59–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2005.03.007>.
- Viscarra Rossel, R.A., Behrens, T., Ben-Dor, E., Brown, D.J., Demattè, J.A.M., Shepherd, K.D., Shi, Z., Stenberg, B., Stevens, A., Adamchuk, V., Aichi, H., Barthès, B.G., Bartholomeus, H.M., Bayer, A.D., Bernoux, M., Böttcher, K., Brodský, L., Du, C.W., Chappell, A., Fouad, Y., Genot, V., Gomez, C., Grunwald, S., Gubler, A., Guerrero, C., Hedley, C.B., Knadel, M., Morrás, H.J.M., Nocita, M., Ramirez-Lopez, L., Roudier, P., Campos, E.M.R., Sanborn, P., Sellitto, V.M., Sudduth, K.A., Rawlins, B.G., Walter, C., Winowiecki, L.A., Hong, S.Y., Ji, W., 2016. A global spectral library to characterize the world's soil. *Earth-Science Rev.* 155, 198–230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2016.01.012>.
- Walker, B.H., Ludwig, D., Holling, C.S., Peterman, R.M., 1981. Stability of semi-arid savanna grazing systems. *J. Ecol.* 69, 473–498. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2259679>.
- Wallach, R., Ben-Arie, O., Graber, E.R., 2005. Soil water repellency induced by long-term irrigation with treated sewage effluent. *J. Environ. Qual.* 34, 1910–1920. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2005.0073>.
- Wang, Z., Wu, Q.J., Wu, L., Ritsema, C.J., Dekker, L.W., Feyen, J., 2003. Effects of water repellency on infiltration rate and flow instability, in: Ritsema, C.J., Dekker, L.W. (Eds.), *Soil Water Repellency – Occurrence, Consequences, and Amelioration*. Elsevier, Amsterdam, pp. 235–244. 10.1016/B978-0-444-51269-7.50024-2.
- Wenjun, J., Zhou, S., Jingyi, H., Shuo, L., 2014. In situ measurement of some soil properties in paddy soil using visible and near-infrared spectroscopy. *PLoS One* 9 (8), e105708.
- Wise, J.E., Mars, J.C., 2022. Field reflectance measurements at night of beach and desert sands within a particulate BRDF model. *Remote Sens.* 14, 5020. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14195020>.
- Xu, H., Zhang, L., Huang, W., Li, X., Si, X., Xu, W., Song, Q., 2020. On-board absolute radiometric calibration and validation based on solar diffuser of HY-1C SCS. *Guangxue Xuebao/Acta Opt. Sin.* 40, 30015–30034. <https://doi.org/10.3788/AOS202040.0928002>.
- Yang, Y., Hu, X., Cao, X., Jin, T., Wang, Y., 2021. Medium-term effects of different wildfire severities on soil properties: a case study of Hengduan Mountains, southwestern China. *IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci.* 861 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/861/6/062021>.